

Evaluating the Performance of Supervised Multiple Linear Regression Machine Learning Algorithm in Predicting the Ampacity of Overhead Transmission Lines

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Abstract— This study examines the overhead transmission line ampacity prediction performance of a supervised multiple linear regression machine learning algorithm integrated with the IEEE-738 heat balance equation, using ten years of historical data from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMet) and operational data from the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN) Afam network using a Python environment. Key meteorological factors included ambient temperature, wind velocity, solar radiation, and air pressure, while conductor properties such as emissivity and age were also considered. The aim was to evaluate the performance of supervised multiple regression algorithm to predict the dynamic ampacity of overhead transmission lines. This was achieved by first deriving the ampacity under different weather and line conditions, then deploying the algorithm for real-time dynamic line rating (DLR) prediction to determine its accuracy and speed based on the performance metrics. The IEEE-738 heat balance ampacity derivation results showed that the 450A-rated conductors had ampacity between 309A and 1406A (62% to 312% of the rated value) while the 630A-rated lines ranged from 380A to 1897A (60% to 301%), implying that depending on the weather conditions and other parameters, overhead transmission lines dynamic ampacity can increase up to 212% and decrease up to about 40% of the rated values of the lines' conductors. On the other hand, the prediction results of the Multiple Regression Machine Learning Algorithm showed a coefficient of determination 0.8912, a Standard Deviation of 0.0021, Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of 56.03, Mean Square Error (MSE) of 3139.32, and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 39.64 within a computing time of 0.9 second. While the prediction speed is very good, it is recommended that other supervised machine learning algorithms should be deployed with the same data to compare their prediction accuracy.

Keywords: Ampacity Prediction, Dynamic Line Rating (DLR), Machine Learning Algorithms, Overhead Transmission Lines, Random Forest Regression

I. INTRODUCTION

Electricity has been the bedrock of economic development globally and recent advancement in technology has placed a higher demand for electricity across the globe. Overhead transmission lines are used to transport electricity from the generating stations to distribution sub-centres (Liang et al., 2018) and the quantity of electricity transported to the distribution end depends on the wheeling capacity of the transmission lines. This wheeling capacity is hinged on the current-carrying capacity (ampacity) of the overhead transmission lines without exceeding its maximum temperature rating. In Nigeria as in most climates, the ampacity of overhead transmission lines are static because the overcurrent and distance protection relays are programmed to initiate tripping signals once the values reach the set threshold. The drawback to this is that it does not allow for the transmission lines to be

optimized as they are mostly underutilized and sometimes over-utilized by control room operators, implying that the exact wheeling capacity of the lines at any instance of time cannot be ascertained statically, but dynamically. According to Nguyen et al. (2013), a conductor's ampacity is the maximum steady electrical current that will meet the design, security, and safety criteria (that is, electrical clearance) of a specific line on which the conductor is employed and plays a crucial role in determining the efficient and reliable transmission of electrical power. Predicting ampacity of overhead transmission lines (OTLs) is a difficult subject that is dependent on a wide array of factors including types of conductors, weather conditions, and the layouts of the lines. Engineers and academics working in the field of electrical power engineering have over the years struggled to precisely predict ampacity of OTLs due to the complexities involved in it.

Electrical power systems are designed to deliver consistent and reliable voltage to end users Amadi et al (2025). Machine learning, a sub-division of artificial intelligence, finds applications in different industries and among the most prominent use of machine learning is predictive modeling, which includes making forecasts about the future by analyzing past data (Wang and Srinivasan, 2017). Supervised regression machine learning algorithms have become increasingly popular in recent years given their capacity to predict continuous output variables. They can be trained with historical data to forecast future possibilities with a high level of exactitude. In the context of electrical power systems, supervised regression machine learning algorithms have been used for a variety of applications such as forecasting electricity demand, optimizing energy consumption, and predicting energy prices.

The deployment of supervised regression machine learning algorithms for predicting OTLs ampacity is novel in the electrical power industry. By utilizing historical data, machine learning algorithms can be trained to predict OTLs ampacity based on various input parameters. The correctness of the prediction can be improved by incorporating new data into the model, making it an invaluable tool for the electrical power industry. The goal of this paper is to utilize supervised multiple regression machine learning algorithm for the real-time prediction of dynamic ampacity of overhead transmission lines with historical weather and transmission lines parameters as inputs.

Figure 1: Typical Overhead Transmission Line

Source: RAX Industry (2021). Overhead Power Line and the Ultimate Guide. <https://www.hbjinyong.com/overhead-transmission-line-guide/>.

Alberdi et al. (2021) introduced a methodology for predicting ampacity of overhead transmission lines for minute-to-day-ahead horizons. The method relied on statistically adapting mesoscale weather predictions to local conditions measured on-site. Given the probabilistic nature of these forecasts, the new

methods focused on the dependability of the safest probability level; that is, those with the lowest probability of beyond the Maximum Allowable Conductor Temperature (MACT) which are subsequently chosen for grid operation. According to the researchers, the proposed approach underwent testing on a distribution line that crosses complex topographies. Furthermore, to overcome the limitations of existing assessment methods for stochastic forecasts, the paper introduced an assessment criterion for ampacity prediction and analyzed line capacity usage alongside it.

Safari et al. (2022) carried out a study on the accurate short-term forecast of Overhead Line (OHL) transmission current-carrying capacity. The researchers proposed a reliable and precise probabilistic model for forecasting the dynamic thermal line rating (DTLR) one hour in advance. By integrating historical climatology data and latent variables acquired through DTLR computation, they enhanced the deep learning framework. Moreover, the authors introduced a tailored cost function to train the deep neural network, considering the security of DTLR based on the desired Probability of Exceedance (POE) while reducing differences from the true values. The validity of their proposed probabilistic DTLR model was established through recorded experimental data, demonstrating its superiority over existing prediction models.

The authors appropriately emphasized the significance of precise DTLR forecasting for effective power system management and strategizing. They highlighted the limitations of traditional approaches, such as Static Transmission Loading Relief (STLR), which tend to exhibit excessive caution, leading to suboptimal utilization of available OHL capacity. To address this issue, they proposed various DTLR models to enable the safe monitoring of OHL thermal conditions and the unlocking of additional capacity and recognized DTLR as a critical factor in aiding the incorporation of renewable energy systems (RESs) into the existing energy infrastructure. The authors noted that existing probabilistic models often make assumptions that fail to capture the non-stationary and intricate interdependencies among meteorological variables and DTLR.

Consequently, the authors introduced a novel probabilistic DTLR prediction model built on deep learning techniques. The recommended framework integrated latent variables and employed a stacked denoising autoencoder (SDAE) to perform unsupervised feature learning and extraction. By utilizing the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model as a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), the researchers accurately captured both long-term and short-term dependencies present in the dataset. The model was trained to achieve the desired point of operation (POE) by employing a customized cost function that

adheres to relevant standards. To assess the performance of their proposed model, the authors conducted a cross-analysis with existing models using publicly accessible data. The results clearly demonstrated the dominance of the proposed model with respect to precision and dependability.

In summary, Safari et al. (2022) provided a valuable contribution to the field by presenting a secure and precise probabilistic DTLR prediction model. Their methodology effectively addressed the presence of unobserved variables, incorporating a Stacked Denoising Autoencoder (SDAE) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architecture, and employing a tailored loss function for training the model. The proposed model, the researchers stated, exhibited superior performance compared to existing prediction models, offering dependable and precise hour-ahead DTLR predictions.

Konstantinou et al. (2019) presented a paper on “Probabilistic Ampacity Forecasting for Overhead Transmission Line” at the 2019 International Conference on Smart Energy Systems and Technologies (SEST). The researchers based their presentation on the continuously growing incorporation of renewable energy sources which puts pressure on the power systems' operation, exemplifying that the transmission system is frequently operated close to its operational limits to serve the increased generation of renewable sources located far from the demand centers. Furthermore, Konstantinou et al. (2019) stated that the thermal rating of overhead transmission lines varies, mainly due to different weather situations like wind speed and air temperature close to the conductors and notwithstanding this fact, the common practice was to use a conservative static seasonal estimation of the current carrying capacity, based on harshest weather conditions. From the foregoing, the researchers focused on the exploitation of forecasting techniques, to determine a probabilistic dynamic line rating. They proposed and tested a methodology on the thermal model of a bare overhead transmission line for ampacity probabilistic forecasting. The study also introduced a methodology to calculate the confidence intervals of the predictions considering the error probability functions of the weather forecasts and presented, according to IEEE Standard 738-2006 (IEEE, 2007), the thermal behaviour of a bare overhead transmission line.

However, the study's methodology for predicting ampacity given the weather conditions near an overhead transmission line was based on the Steady-State Heat Balance Equation which states that heat loss is equal to heat absorption, hence, temperature is constant.

The efficacy of the proposed methodology was assessed through the utilization of a test case scenario. This involved the

examination of weather variables, specifically forecasts, and observations, which were obtained through authentic analysis conducted on an actual site. An overhead conductor was installed at the designated location, adhering to the specifications provided by the vendor for an ACSR 954 CARDINAL conductor. The manufacturer assigned a static rating of 685 A to the conductor. The rating was determined by considering elevated ambient temperatures and windless conditions. The predictions were derived from numerical weather predictions, while the actual ampacity was determined using the ampacity equation, along with measurements of the weather variables. The experimental conditions were conducted over a duration of thirty consecutive days during the summer season. The initial ten-day period was allocated for the computation of error probability mass functions (PMFs), while the subsequent twenty-day period was dedicated to the assessment of the method's performance.

The work by Wei et al. (2016) introduced a new probabilistic forecast method for Dynamic Thermal Rating (DTR) of power transmission lines. The method utilized quantile regression analysis to incorporate weather parameters, improving the accuracy of point predictions and providing prediction results of the probability distribution function. This technology facilitated the integration of DTR into power system operations, enabling better dispatch decision-making.

Four major gaps have been identified from the reviewed literature. Firstly, the input parameters used in machine learning predictions of ampacity in many studies are limited; hence, this study utilizes both historical conductor (transmission line) and weather data to predict the ampacity of overhead transmission lines using supervised regression machine learning algorithms. For example, although Kabović et al. (2018) deployed four weather parameters, namely, temperature, wind speed, wind direction, and solar radiation, to predict ampacity, the study did not consider the age of the conductor, the load current, and the manufacturer's ampacity rating of the conductor. In this study, ambient temperature, wind speed, solar radiation, conductor load current, conductor age and initial (manufacturer's) ampacity are utilized as input parameters to bridge the identified research gap and aid in better predicting ampacity of the overhead transmission lines.

Secondly, some studies that have deployed many input features have relied on a limited amount of historical weather data, typically up to three days, to predict the current-carrying capacity (ampacity) of OTLs. This restricted historical data might lead to predictions that are only valid during specific periods of the year, failing to capture the impact of seasonal variations and long-term weather patterns (climatic changes) on

ampacity. This limitation in the duration of historical data used for prediction presents an additional research gap. This gap is addressed in this study by utilizing two (2) years historical line and weather dataset from 2021 to 2022.

Thirdly, no known study has deployed a supervised multiple regression machine learning algorithm to predict the dynamic ampacity of overhead transmission lines. For instance, Sobhy et al. (2021) examined how renewable energy generation affected power line transmission using only Random Forest (RF) Regression as the machine-learning algorithm, while Jiang et al. (2016) proposed a Principal Component Regression (PCR) based approach. Fourthly, all the real-time ampacity prediction explored above deployed hours-ahead and days-ahead predictions, implying that the Transmission System Operators (TSO) have to rely on those predictions for grid control within the period under consideration. For instance, Gameda and Stork (2022) conducted a 24-hour-ahead real-time ampacity prediction while Molinar et al. (2020) conducted a 2-day-ahead real-time forecasting of ampacity. The drawback with these sorts of real-time ampacity prediction/forecasting is that they do not consider that weather changes can occur within the duration of the forecast; hence, they assume a maximum ampacity threshold that cannot be exceeded within the said period. In practical terms, the interplay of varying weather conditions and conductor parameters even within the shortest possible time make it impractical to assume the maximum ampacity of overhead transmission lines for a long time without over-utilizing the line. It therefore means that the best real-time ampacity prediction should be able to tell the Transmission Service Operators the present current on the conductor and its extra capacity before attaining its maximum point. This is what this research aims to achieve. Ultimately, the main focus of this work is to develop multiple regression model for real-time prediction of ampacity of overhead transmission lines. This study also uses five transmission lines of the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN) namely, Afam-Afam IPP 132kV Lines 1 and 2, Afam IPP-Port Harcourt 132kV Lines 1 and 2 and Afam IPP-Elelenwo 132kV Line 1, as a composite case study, deploys two years of historical weather data of Port Harcourt namely, ambient temperature, wind velocity, wind speed, solar radiation, air pressure, air density, relative humidity, and rainfall, obtained from NiMET and the conductors' parameters obtained from the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The primary materials/resources utilized in this paper include:

- AFAM IPP 132kV Transmission Station historical dataset and transmission line parameters.
- Historical weather data obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMet) and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)
- Python 3 environment (Jupyter) along with packages like pandas, numpy, and sklearn. A 16GB RAM HP Envy Laptop

Methods

This study adopts a data-driven supervised multiple regression framework to predict the ampacity of overhead transmission lines based on meteorological and conductor-related parameters. The methodological workflow consists of data acquisition, preprocessing, feature selection, model development using supervised multiple regression machine learning algorithm and its performance evaluation using certain statistical metrics.

The IEEE 738 Physics-Based Model for Calculating Ampacity

The steady-state ampacity of the five overhead transmission line conductors were calculated using a physics-based model derived from the IEEE Standard 738-2012 heat balance equation. The method computes the equilibrium current at which the rate of heat generated within the conductor equals the rate of heat dissipated to the surrounding environment. This section describes the computational framework, governing equations, and the algorithmic implementation used to generate the ampacity values for each recorded weather condition and conductor parameters for the 50, 000 rows of data.

➤ The Governing Heat Balance Equation

Equation 1 shows the Steady-State Heat Balance Equation for the conductor.

Equation 1 shows the Steady-State Heat Balance Equation for the conductor.

$$q_J + q_S = q_C + q_R \quad (1)$$

where:

$$q_J = \text{Joule Heat (Resistive Heating)}$$

$$q_S = \text{Solar Heat Gain (Sun Radiation Absorbed)}$$

$$q_C = \text{Convective Heat Loss (Air Cooling)}$$

$$q_R = \text{Radiative Heat Loss}$$

However, the resistive heating component part of the equation can be rewritten as

$$q_f = I^2 R(T_s) \quad (2)$$

Where:

I = Current and RT(s) is the conductor's resistance at temperature, T_s (Ohm/m)

Equation 1 can then be rewritten as:

$$I^2 RT(s) + q_c = q_c + q_R \quad (3)$$

Therefore, by making I, the subject of formulae:

$$I = \sqrt{\frac{q_c + q_R}{RT(s)}} \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 is the IEEE 738 Physics-model for calculating ampacity of overhead transmission lines under steady-state conditions, neglecting transient heating and cooling effects. Equation 4 is derived.

Air Property Correlations

$$T_f = \frac{T_s + T_a}{2} + 237.15 \quad (5)$$

At this temperature, the following empirical relations were applied:

i. Dynamic Viscosity (Sutherland's Law):

$$\mu = \frac{1.458 \times 10^{-6} - 6T_f^{1.5}}{T_f + 110.4} \quad (6)$$

ii. Thermal Conductivity:

$$k = 0.0241 + 7.72 \times 10^{-5} (T_f - 273.15) \quad (7)$$

iii. Kinematic Viscosity:

$$v = \frac{\mu}{\rho} \quad (8)$$

iv. Thermal Expansion Coefficient:

$$\beta = \frac{1}{T_f} \quad (9)$$

These correlations are valid for standard atmospheric conditions between 250–350 K.

Convective and Radiative Heat Transfer

Convective Heat Loss (q_C):

The model takes into consideration for both forced and natural convection around a horizontal cylinder.

The effective crosswind component is given by:

$$V_{\perp} = V |\sin \theta| \quad (10)$$

Dimensionless parameters were evaluated as:

$$R_e = \frac{\rho V_{\perp} D}{\mu} \quad (11)$$

$$G_r = \frac{g \beta (T_s - T_a) D^3}{\nu^2} \quad (12)$$

By combining the forced and natural convection, the total Nusselt Number was determined:

$$Nu_f = 0.3 + \frac{0.62 Re^{1/2} Pr^{1/3}}{[1 + (0.4/Pr)^{1/4}]^{1/4}} [1 + (Re/282000)^{5/8}]^{4/5} \quad (13)$$

$$Nu_n = (G_r Pr)^{1/4} \quad (14)$$

$$Nu = (Nu_f^4 + Nu_n^4)^{1/4} \quad (15)$$

The convective heat-transfer coefficient and heat loss were then obtained as follows:

$$\text{Convective Heat - Transfer Coefficient, } h = \frac{k Nu}{D}$$

$$Q_C = \pi D h (T_s^* - T_a^*) \quad (16)$$

(b) Radiative Heat Loss (Q_R)

$$Q_C = \pi D \sigma \epsilon (T_s^{*4} - T_a^{*4}) \quad (17)$$

Where:

$$\sigma = 5.670 \times 10^{-8} \frac{W}{m^2 K^4} \text{ is the Stefan Boltzmann Constant}$$

(c) Solar Heat Gain (q_S)

$$q_s = \alpha_s S D \quad (18)$$

Electrical Resistance Correction

The conductor's resistance was adjusted for the operating temperature as:

$$RT(s) = \frac{R_{20}}{1000} [1 + \alpha_{20} (T_s - 20)] \quad (19)$$

Equation 19 converts resistance from Ω/km to Ω/m and compensates for thermal effects.

The ampacity for each of the 50,000 observations was therefore calculated using Equation 4 above. Invalid or physically inconsistent cases (negative heat balance or zero resistance) were automatically set to NaN to prevent numerical errors.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the ampacity prediction of overhead transmission lines using a supervised multiple regression machine learning algorithm and the evaluation of the

algorithm. In this paper, the results of the predictions of overhead transmission are presented in tables and plots. The performance metrics results for the supervised multiple regression machine learning algorithm, are also presented using the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and the Coefficient of Determination (r^2) respectively. The section concludes with a discussion of the results presented.

Discussion of Results of the Predicted Ampacity against Calculated and Rated Ampacity of the Case Study Transmission Lines

As seen in Table 1, the five highest and lowest predicted ampacity for each case-study transmission line for the deployed machine learning algorithm are presented. Also, the manufacturer's rated and calculated ampacity, the original row number of the extracted information as well as the status of the line are presented.

The Afam IPP–Eledenwo 132 kV Line 1, rated 630 A, recorded a maximum ampacity of 1897 A under favourable weather conditions, representing 301% of and 201% increase to its rated ampacity at an ambient temperature of 20.7 °C, a wind velocity of 28.9 m/s, a wind attack angle of 270°, and solar radiation of 191 W/m². This clearly shows that, under these conditions, convective heat transfer was very high, thereby enhancing the speedy removal of heat from the surface of the conductor. On the other hand, at 38.1 °C, 0.0 m/s, and 1023 W/m², the conductor's current-carrying capacity reduced to 380 A, implying that the conductor was only at 60.32% of and 39.68% decrease to its rated ampacity. The reduction resulted from low convection, high air temperature, and high solar radiation that increased surface temperature and resistance.

Similarly, the Afam IPP–Port Harcourt 132kV Line 2, rated 450 A, reached a maximum of 1402A representing 312 % of and 212% increase to the rated ampacity at 20.7 °C, 28.9 m/s, and 577 W/m², however, at 38.1 °C, 0.0 m/s, and 987 W/m², the line attained its minimum ampacity of 278A, implying that only 62% of its rated ampacity could be utilized safely at the weather states above. This, again, is consistent with the steady-state heat balance equation.

More so, the Afam–Afam IPP 132kV Line 2, rated 630 A, attained 1883A, which is 299% of and 199% increase to rated ampacity at 20.7 °C, 28.9 m/s, and 868 W/m², but reduced to 387A, which is 61% of its rated ampacity at 39.2 °C, 0.0 m/s, and 864 W/m². The Afam IPP–Port Harcourt 132kV Line 1, rated 450 A, attained 1400A, which is 311 % of and 211% increase to the rated ampacity at 20.7 °C, 28.9 m/s, and 733 W/m², but dropped to 309A, which is 69% of and 21% decrease

from the rated ampacity at 39.2 °C, 0.0 m/s, and 426 W/m². Finally, the Afam–Afam IPP 132kV Line 1, rated 450A, attained 1406A which is 313% of and 213% increase to the line's rated ampacity at 20.7 °C, 28.9 m/s, and 283 W/m², whereas it reduced to 295A at 39.2 °C, 0.0 m/s, and 640 W/m², signifying that only 66% of the line's ampacity could be safely utilized at the time.

In all the five case-study 132kV transmission lines, it has been consistently revealed that high ampacity values correlated with strong cross-wind, low temperature and moderate solar radiation whereas low ampacity values corresponded with low wind speed, high air temperature, and high solar radiation. This pattern shows that conductor ampacity is mainly a function of wind speed/velocity, ambient temperature, and solar irradiance. Under cool and windy conditions, convective cooling dominates the steady-state thermal balance, enhancing greater heat dissipation, whereas solar absorption dominates in hot and low/non-windy conditions, resulting in the rises of conductor surface temperature, increases in resistance, and consequently, reduced overhead transmission lines' ampacity.

These results conform to the physical principles described in IEEE Std 738 (2023). The standard explains that ampacity depends on the equilibrium between internal Joule heating and external heat exchange through convection, radiation, and solar gain. The Churchill and Bernstein (1977) correlation for circular cylinders in cross-flow also shows that convective heat transfer rises with wind speed and attack angle, supporting the high ampacity observed under strong cross-wind.

The findings agree with previous empirical studies. Karimi et al. (2018) observed that wind velocity and direction contribute over 80 % of the variability in dynamic line rating, while temperature and solar irradiance contribute secondary effects. Additionally, the International Renewable Energy Agency (2020), stated that extreme convective conditions can increase transmission lines ampacity by between 100% to 200%. These published results confirm that wind-driven convection and solar loading are the major determinants of ampacity.

The observed range of 60–313 % of rated capacity across all lines is physically justified. Static ratings are defined for the most adverse thermal conditions which are representative of conservative limits; that is, high ambient temperature, low wind, and high solar intensity. In reality, when conditions are favourable, ampacity can safely exceed rated capacity by more than 200 %, while under extreme heat and calm air it can fall below the nominal rating. This validates the application of Dynamic Line Rating systems that adjust allowable current according to real-time meteorological data.

Holistically, these results confirm the accuracy of the IEEE 738 model and its suitability for tropical climates such as southern Nigeria. The observed dependence of ampacity on wind speed, ambient temperature, and solar radiation aligns with theoretical expectations and global best practice. The agreement with findings from IEEE, CIGRÉ, and IRENA further supports the recommendation to integrate real-time weather monitoring into transmission operations to improve efficiency and prevent thermal overloading.

Based on the calculated ampacity of each of the transmission lines, the multiple regression machine learning algorithm prediction results recorded a coefficient of determination (r^2) of 0.8912, a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 56.03A, a Mean Square Error (MSE) of 3139.32, and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 39.64A under 0.9 second as seen in Tables 1 and 2. The processing speed of 0.9second shows that the algorithm is very suitable for real-time dynamic line rating prediction as it can compute the ampacity within such limited time. The approximate 0.90 coefficient of determination also shows that the multiple regression algorithm deployed in this study can predict the ampacity correctly 90% of the time. The error metrics as already shown above also reflect the margins of error of the algorithm implying that the foundational linear formula has limitations in computing weather or conductor parameters which have non-linear relationships with ampacity. Additionally, Figures 1 to 5 show the degree of correlations between the rated, calculated and predicted ampacity of the five case-study transmission lines deployed in this study. In the figures, the dotted red line represents the static ampacity or rating of the line, the black line corresponds to the calculated ampacity whereas the blue line is the predicted ampacity of the lines. Also, the figures clearly shows, in consonance with Table 1, that the actual/calculated ampacity/rating of overhead transmission lines can either be lower or higher than the static ampacity depending on the interplay of weather. The overlap of the blue and black lines in each of the case-study plots as seen in Figures 1 to 5 reveal the extent of the correlation between the actual/calculated and the predicted ampacity

Table 1: Top 5 Highest and Lowest Calculated and Predicted Ampacity Per Transmission Line Using the Multiple Regression Machine Learning Algorithm.

Line Name	Algorithm	Original Row Number (in	Electric demand (A)	Rated Ampacity(A)	Calculated Ampacity (A)	Predicted Ampacity (A)
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		CSV)				
Afam IPP-Elele nwo L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	6617	364.0	630	1862.6966	1957.7
Afam IPP-Elele nwo L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	9968	323.8	630	1869.56711	1945.97
Afam IPP-Elele nwo L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	8157	339.6	630	1897.0762	1944.53
Afam – IPP-Elele nwo L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	8839	12.7	630	1857.7047	1931.23
Afam – IPP-Elele nwo L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	5282	143.1	630	1787.8233	1925.93
Afam – IPP-Elele nwo L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	7113	161.7	630	380.0852	712.73
Afam – IPP-Elele nwo L1	Multiple Linear Regression	6778	93.4	630	419.5859	719.11

	(MLR)					
Afam – IPP- Elele nwo L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	4558	363.5	630	472.2279	728.01
Afam – IPP- Elele nwo L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	5805	158.2	630	464.5227	728.57
Afam – IPP- Elele nwo L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	7468	423.2	630	502.4357	729.71
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	16617	364.0	450	1379.4333	1714.8
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	18839	12.7	450	1384.7435	1711.2
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	18157	339.6	450	1406.4458	1707.41
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion	19968	323.8	450	1382.3050	1699.18

	(MLR)					
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	18956	184.5	450	1371.9640	1678.86
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	16778	93.4	450	295.6265	481.09
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	17468	423.2	450	348.7824	481.22
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	15805	158.2	450	327.2082	487.33
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	16311	127.0	450	402.8595	494.07
Afam – Afam IPP L1	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion (MLR)	19861	189.8	450	383.8991	497.39
Afam – Afam IPP L2	Multi ple Linear Regre ssion	26617	364.0	630	1873.3805	1975.67

	(MLR)					
Afam — Afam IPP L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	28839	12.7	630	1866.1888	1945.45
Afam — Afam IPP L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	29968	323.8	630	1861.8850	1933.08
Afam — Afam IPP L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	28157	339.6	630	1883.2764	1921.07
Afam — Afam IPP L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	25282	143.1	630	1783.8535	1919.56
Afam — Afam IPP L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	26778	93.4	630	386.9089	707.26
Afam — Afam IPP L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	26311	127.0	630	514.9219	714.73
Afam — Afam IPP L2	Multiple Linear Regression	27468	423.2	630	488.1219	723.34

	(MLR)					
Afam — Afam IPP L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	27113	161.7	630	412.7424	724.39
Afam — Afam IPP L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	21904	169.7	630	484.7391	728.78
Afam — IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	36617	364.0	450	1383.9857	1726.1
Afam — IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	38839	12.7	450	1387.2215	1717.37
Afam — IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	39968	323.8	450	1382.0816	1698.63
Afam — IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	35282	143.1	450	1328.0169	1694.74
Afam — IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression	38157	339.6	450	1400.2587	1691.81

	(MLR)											
Afam – IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	36778	93.4	450	309.2785	488.51						
Afam – IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	39181	274.3	450	408.5370	500.07						
Afam – IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	35426	251.3	450	416.8237	500.55						
Afam – IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	35805	158.2	450	350.0566	501.24						
Afam – IPP-PH L1	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	37113	161.7	450	319.0299	501.72						
Afam IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	46617	364.0	450	1384.8776	1728.32						
Afam IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression	49968	323.8	450	1385.7901	1707.85						
Afam IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	48839	12.7	450			48839	12.7	450	1382.2470	1705.00	
Afam IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	48157	339.6	450			48157	339.6	450	1402.4066	1697.22	
Afam IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	40516	225.0	450			40516	225.0	450	1269.0235	1686.41	
Afam IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	47113	161.7	450			47113	161.7	450	278.6784	480.06	
Afam IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	47468	423.2	450			47468	423.2	450	349.4456	481.64	
Afam IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	45805	158.2	450			45805	158.2	450	323.1138	484.94	
Afam IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression	49181	274.3	450			49181	274.3	450	393.8198	489.46	

	(MLR)					
Afam-IPP-PH L2	Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)	46778	93.4	450	317.9532	493.4

Table 2: Ampacity Prediction Performance Metrics of the Multiple Regression Machine Algorithm

Model	r^2 Score	Std. Dev	RMSE	MSE	MAE	Computing Time
Multiple Linear Regression	0.8912	0.0021	56.0296	3139.3172	39.6400	0.9 second

Figure 1: Plot of Actual vs Predicted Ampacity of Afam IPP-Elelenwo 132kV Line 1 Using Multiple Regression Algorithm

Figure 2: Plot of Actual vs Predicted Ampacity on Afam-Afam IPP 132kV Line 1 Using Multiple Regression Algorithm

Figure 3: Plot of Actual vs Predicted Ampacity of Afam-Afam IPP 132kV Line 2 Using Multiple Regression Algorithm

Figure 4: Plot of Actual vs Predicted Ampacity of Afam IPP-Port Harcourt 132kV Line 1 Using Multiple Regression Algorithm

Figure 5: Plot of Actual vs Predicted Ampacity of Afam IPP-Port Harcourt 132kV Line 2 Using Multiple Regression Algorithm

IV. CONCLUSION

This study employed the steady-state heat balance equation as the basis to calculate the actual dynamic ampacity of overhead transmission lines within the Afam network of the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN), given for changing weather conditions and specified conductor parameters. It then developed a supervised multiple regression machine learning algorithm to predict the dynamic line rating (dynamic ampacity) of the five (5) transmission lines. It collected historical electrical power and weather data from Afam IPP 132kV Transmission Station and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMeT) respectively, pre-processed and prepared the collected data, trained and tested the machine learning (ML) algorithms using the prepared training and test data, and evaluated the performance of the algorithm with commonly used performance metrics, namely Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and the Coefficient of Determination. The ampacity calculation results show that despite the manufacturer's 450A rated current-carrying capacity (ampacity) of the Hitech 160mm² Aluminium Conductor Steel Reinforced (ACSR) of Afam-Afam IPP 132kV Transmission Line 1 and Afam IPP-Port Harcourt 132kV Transmission Lines 1 and 2, and the 630A ampacity of the 250mm² Bear Aluminium Conductor Steel Reinforced (ACSR) of Afam-Afam IPP 132kV Line 2 and Afam IPP-Elelenwo 132kV Transmission Line 1, the real-time ampacity of the lines can be lower or higher depending on the interplay of weather conditions and the conductor parameters. On the other hand, the findings of the study reveal that the supervised multiple regression machine learning algorithm can predict the current a transmission line can carry in real-time (dynamic ampacity) to 90% accuracy within a computing 9 seconds although some of the error metrics are somewhat high. Accordingly, it is recommended that other supervised regression machine learning algorithms should be deployed with the same dataset and the results compared before adopting the best in speed and accuracy.

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